

Character Toys: Toying with Identity, Playing with Emotion

Rémi Leclerc - School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hung Hom, Hong Kong, (852) 2766 5492, sdremi@polyu.edu.hk

Conference theme: Values and Culture, Toy & Game Design

Keywords: Character Toy Design, Emotion, Youth Culture

Abstract

Why do we produce licensed toys? What compels children and adults alike to desire such objects? What makes them such greatly sought after artifacts by collectors?

Products of the XXth century, licensed, or character toys, are offspring of the toy and media industries. Surfing the post-war consumer wave generated by the Baby Boom, the toy industry was eager to transform the war effort's technological know-how to explore new global market options. Mass-mediated pop-culture characters were seen as a boon for marketers keen on tapping into a wider mental share of consumers' emotions and fantasies to fuel innovation and fend off internationalized competition.

Designs and play patterns generated by the reification of a popular myth derive from an original narrative; they are the interface to a world of motivations and values. Character toys mediate play, and as such combine play with story telling, inviting players to identify to role models, adapt adventures to their social needs and act out their emotional development.

The growing interest for character toys has generated a number of publications, especially in the US and Japan where production and export of images – and toys – are among the world's highest. However, despite nostalgic introductions meant to remind readers of an idealised childhood, few say much about the emotional dynamics generated as one interacts with character toys. Only recently have we seen attempts made to analyse the phenomenon's evolution, in order to anchor it in a wider cultural context. This paper relates character toys'

impact on current consumer culture, its value as a collector item, and its relevance to emotion and desirability (i.e. the worthiness of these artefacts in regard to an individual's self-realisation) to current toy design practices.

Introduction: Pop Culture, Mass Media, Plastics

The outcome of a very diverse set of situations, the emergence of a popular character is fascinating because it reflects a moment. 50% of all toys sold in the world are consumed by adults, many of these collectors working at preserving such "moments". The nostalgic, emotional drive partly motivating these amateur curators in their exciting treasure hunts results in a play of signs gleaned from the zeitgeist; and while collectors may be satisfying very personal desires, playfully rearranging notions of self and identity, their dive in an immediate past sometimes reveals the future: character toys and the popular culture associated with youth are central to contemporary culture and reflect the emotional *air du temps* of past, present and future generations.

The success of such toys relies on the popularity generated by characters, or myths, from which they have been derived. Children and adult players alike are keen to integrate these characters' values as they help channel a host of emotions to provide access to symbolic meaning, verifying Roland Barthes' contention that "objects are initiators: they are infinitely faster culture mediators than ideas, as powerful producers of fantasy as 'situations'."

Leading French copyrights lawyer Gérard Bigle explains that "Capitalising on the derived rights of a product enables the businessman to increase the power of attraction of his product and to improve considerably his chances to sell it. Between a plain product and one decorated with a character, the consumer will very likely choose the second one." (in *Droits Derivés, Licences et Character Merchandising*, 1987) Licensing relies on positive feedback: a widely advertised artwork entices consumers' desire for its merchandise, which reciprocally promotes the original product.

US toy manufacturer Ideal had as early as 1903 negotiated with then American President Theodore Roosevelt the rights to manufacture a plush toy named Teddy Bear after a 1902 Washington Post cartoon reported him ordering the mercy killing of a wounded young bear at a hunting party. Teddy Bear has comforted countless children, been cajoled, or offered as a token of love to children and adults alike. Probably the toy that has been the receptacle of the cuddliest emotions ever manufactured, the Teddy Bear was also the first mass-marketed character toy. Countless versions have populated rooms and bed tops all around the world since 1903.

However Bigle suggests American businessman Kay Kamen initiated in 1932 the first real licensing strategy, generalized in the thirties for the exploitation of derivative rights for Walt Disney Studio's many characters.

Toys have since then been the product foundation on which character licensing programs are established, as licenses are seen by most manufacturers as safe market investment: sales of toys produced under license recurrently top all toy category sales figures.

A Breath of Fresh Air

To fully understand the circumstances in which these toys came to be calls for a brief account of their historical background. Their apparition is by no means fortuitous.

Up to World War II, toys played a predetermined part in the education of children. They varied according to family, social, cultural and professional customs, and to children's gender. The purpose was to familiarise the child to his/her future life in an adult world. Boys were expected to take on their fathers' trades, girls were taught the means to manage domestic life.

The industrial revolution and the rise of the middle class led to an elaborate social code, which the toy industry adopted up until today, and which are a lure for children. As Maria Lluisa Borrás contends in *The World of Toys* (1969); "Playing with toys puts the child in contact with notions which he acquires before even understanding them".

Although XIXth century values are still supported by the advent of consumerism and new means of communication, new cultural references brought about by the war have come into being. By the end of World War II the toy industry is at a standstill. Production must be given a new start. New cultural models developed by the industrial society redefine its role by widening its scope: a breath of fresh air then blows through the industry. New economic values and the development of modern communication means now enable the industry to produce and distribute licensed toys at a scale never seen before.

A new field of activity for the toy business, character toys forms obviously fruitful links between educational values and economic ones, while in other cases these artifacts may represent to parents and educators a subversive type of media or in some cases are seen as counter-culture fetish. Resulting from the conjunction of commerce, industry and the media, this type of toy didn't reach full maturity until late 1945. Three historical factors started it off: post-war baby boom, plastics and the rising popularity of television.

Stemming from traditional folklore, popularising classical and antique culture, mass culture propagates a revised form of mythology: science, technology, democracy, liberalism, the eternal struggle between good and evil are the modern backdrops for its heroes.

The characters inhabiting contemporary children's tales have become these iconic creatures, praising or condemning modern civilisation's values. The media familiarize and fascinate their young audience with these characters, while frequent and regular broadcasts hold their attention. But seeing and hearing is not enough: they need to pass through the screen, touch, smell, taste, hug... get inside the characters' bodies, possess their soul.

Close Encounters of the Third Kind: Trash Culture

The development of any new form of media raises questions about our ability to handle its moral – indeed, emotional – excesses.

Expectedly this sub-culture has many detractors. They are joined by those who consider that exploitation of artwork for profit should not be allowed. “Licensed products are pointless; they are mere gadgets of no practical use to the consumer. Worse, buying them results in overconsumption; for some, even, it is an insidious manner to propagate harmful ideologies preventing the consumer from making a personal choice (consumers' comments to Bigle) These words could echo New York City Hospitals Head of Psychiatry Dr Frederic Wertham 1954's *Seduction of the Innocent* denouncing the excessive immorality present, according to him, in comic books liable to pervert the minds of American youths.

Earlier in the States the 1934 Hays Code drastically controlled levels of what was seen as appropriate on the Silver Screen.

Today, a quick scan of several websites reveals that children from the States to Hong Kong spend between 40 to 45 hours in front of a screen every week: it is hardly surprising that some consumers should raise the alarm. Many feel lost in a world where the close association between the media and industrial production drives people to buy even more images and products as a means to satisfy wants fuelled by... the consumer industry. Character toys are a perfect example of this association, as they are presented to young children in the form of three-dimensional role models.

So are character toys trash? In Toyland, these are children's close encounters of the third kind: the process takes children from discovery to physical encounter through observation of contemporary mythology. Through his/her “thing”, he/she accesses a world of fantasy. Also, the affective links children entertain with this often poetic and humourous environment may allow

them to view the drab world their parents are preparing for them with objectivity and sometimes, amusement.

Idol Worship, Collection, Manipulation, Transposition: Perversions

Typically a character toy blends virtual and tangible consumer products; the character/sign and toy/object in a reified icon, a fetish players and collectors identify with as it carries an idealized reflection of one's identity and status.

Children and adults alike - collectors, antiquaries or industrialists for the latter – all fall victim to character toys' spell. The magnetic power of these reified icons, to which one needs to add the playful and educational functions traditionally the domain of any other toy category attracts a heterogeneous following of players, collectors, and culture vultures - a passionate cohort of young people aged, to paraphrase Belgian comic-book hero Tintin author Hergé, "7 to 77".

The moment one group ceases to abuse these objects from overplay; the other saves them from the bin and oblivion, pampers and preserves them to display with pride, giving them a renewed, gentrified lease on life, satisfied with the feeling that one has performed a ritual act of salvation – a rite of salvation of oneself, really; providing the nostalgic player with an emotional lifeline to an idealised sense of self.

Yet the crowd this form of nostalgia affects gets younger every year. In *Arrested Development: Pop Culture and the Erosion of Adulthood*, University of East London Lecturer Andrew Calcutt notes that where older generations became nostalgic for the past because that is where their lives and experiences are, today's young adults appear to hold onto their childhoods as a "comfort blanket" against the future: young adults' obsession with their recent childhoods suggests they might feel uncertain about their own futures.

"Nostalgia ain't what it used to be", says Calcutt. "When 'youth culture' first went back to its roots in the 70s, it went in search of seemingly significant qualities such as authenticity. Today's pop culture is more likely to revel in its own insignificance, as shown in the nostalgia for silly toys and faddish fashion rather than for anything more serious."

"Older people have a reason to be nostalgic. Most of their life is behind them. That young people are looking over their shoulder so much is a sign of underconfidence, I think. The reassuring thing about the past is that we already know the outcome."

Browsing the postmodern hyperchoice just a click away their seniors would not have dreamt of only a generation ago, contemporary youth gets to pick its identity from a virtual wardrobe – and literally indexes it for others to view: on the web, *cosplay* (costume play) is a virtually incessant game of mirrors where self is lost. The step from *manga* (Japanese comic books) to

mantra is easy to collate – but hard to qualify – is a self that is clicked and uploaded the real deal? “If everyone is hip... is anyone hip?” cheekily asked TIME Magazine in its August 8, 1994 cover story.

Whether assimilating a hero’s attributes to oneself or displaying it on a shelf, the relationship is that of a bittersweet form of insanity: get as close as possible to an imaginary hero, even if this means substituting “I” *again-again* by another, and another, and another... in a serial play of evolutionary identification by juxtaposition or transposition.

The Collector: a Nostalgic or a Curator?

Playing this subtle, complex game of mirrors, character toy collectors seem to gain an apparent form of serenity, a relatively precarious and unstable neurotic equilibrium, which remains at the mercy of their own existential interrogations perverted by the cult to their heroes.

Jean Baudrillard’s analysis of collection as an activity in his *System of Objects* (1968) may serve to illustrate this passionate relationship between (mostly male) humans and these objects. For Baudrillard, collecting is a game, one between a “qualitative quintessence”, the collector-subject singularity, hungry for signs of identification in an alienating world on the one side, and “quantitative manipulation”, the possibility of the series, of indefinite substitution, made possible in this case (character toys) by the multiplication of available heroes and characters, the modern means to broadcast their adventures and the industrial proliferation of their artifacts. Everything revolves around the self, explains Baudrillard. “In a collection, each and every object refers to one another as they refer ultimately to the subject”. The collection’s high point is the collector himself, having set up a system through which he “attempts to reconstitute a universe, a private totality, in a closed circuit. The object’s absolute singularity emerges to him the moment it is owned by me, which allows me to recognize myself in it as an absolutely singular being.”

I own these character (toys) therefore I am: as one collects, one always collects oneself, thus taking control over emotions of fear and insecurity, and grounding a sense of safety and feelings of empowerment.

The object and its function (here the toy, the hero and its characteristics) becomes irrelevant, substituting itself for an “impassioned abstraction”, where the object – a character toy manufactured under license – is no more specified through its function but qualified by the subject. Exit Batman, Bart Simpson and Bond, James Bond: nothing left but a confused and narcissistic conglomeration of another me, complete with its contradictions, its certitudes, or its doubts, one that I jealously conceal from my environment, but to which I parsimoniously unveil

carefully chosen facets (characters) at the opportune moment, in schizophrenic multicolor combinations à la Rubik's cube.

A collector of characters plays an emotional game of mirrors. Indeed the character toy collection becomes the "narcissistic equivalent of the self. Loss or deterioration of this object signifies castration. One does not lend its phallus, that's all. One looks after and watches over oneself. One enjoys one's self." (Baudrillard)

In the "majestic tautological" act of collecting, the impassioned feelings that very often stifle human relationships such as possessiveness, jealousy, or control, cancel each other and lose their grip on the human/object relationship. "One can look at objects – they will not look back. Hence one commits to the object everything that has not been vested into human relationships". Contrary to the regressive, nostalgic "Closet Collectors", despised by French actor Sacha Guitry, the more mature "Display Collectors", leave their nostalgia in the closet and love to share their passion. For American antique toy collector David Pressland, collectors typically go through three stages: first they gather; then they sort; then finally they show. More aspiring curators than nostalgic amateurs, keeping a sensible, analytical distance from their passion, they are keen to showcase to their contemporaries a sampling of our world conscientiously preserved from oblivion. *Tell me what you collect and I'll tell you who you are.*

Character Toys: Ideal Collector Item?

Alongside role play, emulation, and assimilation of values inherent to heroes, collecting is an essential character toy play activity for the following reasons:

Jean Poirier describes the collector's process of subjective transposition in *Histoire des Moeurs (History of Mores)*: "the collector refuses the object's reification; he considers it as a subject, or a subjective projection of himself, which will allow him to survive himself to his own death. Criteria selected for the non reification of these objects (character toys) are just as innumerable, and subject to transformation, or evolution as the collector's personality itself", whom like an emotional Fregoli, will get into any character of his choice, according to feelings connected to one's place in society.

By attributing value to apparently futile artifacts, collectors gather significant pieces of a bigger cultural puzzle and save entire pages of history. For art chronicler Maurice Rheims, "as with art, the industrial object teaches us about history": one can easily see how character toys' highly emotional value as objects at the crossroads of the cultural, manufacturing and trade industries offers several social legacies.

Working at preserving mass-mediated pop culture entertainment products, one "freezes" society for eternity: a fashion episode, a momentary mediation of its ever changing passions.

XIXth century French social commentator Honoré de Balzac contends that due to their keen sense of observation “it is to collectors’ credit to preempt fashion”. To paraphrase Derrida, archiving character toys, one is concerned with future youth culture precisely because it preserves its past.

Cheap Art, Big Thrills, I Don’t Want to Die

As the contemporary art market increasingly distances itself from people, collectors rely on their instincts and emotions to forge an appreciation of cultural artifacts they can identify with. This mass-media-induced desire is rewarded with instant gratification – pleasure a few dollars away – and the aura of the original work is enshrined in a never-to-be-touched shroud of purity: these are toys not to play with. From the physical manipulation of an object one can rearrange for display, or real play, to the abstract manipulation of one’s sense of identity, the key to one’s emotions lies in the ability to forge a strong sense of personality: character toys are ready-to-consume pop art, easy to appreciate, instantly understood. As one *consumes* the industrial product, one simultaneously *appreciates* the artwork.

Baudrillard, Poirier, and Rheims concede that as a collector surrounds himself with carefully selected objects he struggles against the anxiety generated by the perspective of his own death. By ignoring time’s irreversible nature, the collector eludes death’s inevitability.

For Poirier, it is the subjective projection of one’s personality onto one’s objects that allows one to survive to oneself.

Rheims contends that the collector “lose any feeling of connection to current time”. Time is done away with: collecting hence would allow one to stand out of time, and open a door onto eternity.

Baudrillard observes that is the very act of organizing a collection that acts as a substitute to time. Collecting, a “pastime” activity, alters time’s value – as one collects, one literally lives *out of time*.

As one collects character toys, one remodels one’s identity and relationship to time – an altered self in an altered time, one undergoes a radical shift in his or her own emotional experiences. The spell is broken the moment one considers doing away with such an accumulation: collecting, an act born out of passion, has the collector oscillate back and forth from appetite to disgust in a quasi-instinctive motion – while few collectors bother dwelling on explaining the motivations that started their often life-long endeavor, many chronically confess to their fixation and swear they will give up what may seem to the outsider an addiction to junk. But this wishful thinking only serves to reveal deeply-rooted feelings of guilt that follows the acknowledgement of secretly held feelings of pleasure.

“True” collectors never give up collecting: breaking off a passionate relationship would imply terrible pain - with the end of passion comes the end of life. In order to conjure the “logical and illogical end of passion” (Baudrillard), collectors, forever walking a tight rope, pamper to their feeling of withdrawal, and as they maintain a precarious equilibrium between satisfaction and want, they constantly fuel their appetite for further acquisitions. A collection cannot be completed as there is always a missing piece in a collection: a collection is a construct the purpose of which lies in its incompleteness. “Withdrawal is probably a positive practice, as this is what the subject eventually holds onto objectively. The presence of the final object would *in fine* signify the death of the subject. Its desired absence allows one to enact its own death by symbolizing it in an object.” (Baudrillard)

This one object the collector will probably never acquire, as the final position it is meant to occupy represents “the illusion of a specific finality”, death. Collecting character toys appears to be a relatively reassuring method to overcome such anxiety. One may see behind collectors’ urge to confront the inevitability of their own death similar motives to those of people raising children: different legacies, same anxiety.

Character Toys Today – Toys not to Play With

The emotionally charged relationship one develops with a character toy, one’s *alter-ludo*, or play self, is one at the back of toy designers’ and marketers’ minds. American toy collector Al Marwick’s 1980s magazine *Antique Toy World* series of articles *The Fun Is in the Search* exposed the same interest from different perspectives: “Among all the Americana that is currently on offer, toys have become the “it” thing... everything “toy” will gain in popularity in the 90s, with the risk that this phenomenon could well succumb to its own success. (...) Obviously dealers and their lot (collectors) have already uncovered us – we can expect their hordes among us in the next decade.”

This money/affect cocktail has had a perverse effect on the toy industry. Manufacturers are happy to cash in on toys’ inherent nostalgic and artistic streak to sell a population of indiscriminating adult consumers ready-made nostalgic experiences in the form of re-editions of past products such as early Mickey Mouse wooden puppets or Raggedy Ann dolls.

In the mid-eighties the growing respectability of the comic book art in France started off a high-end industry of high-quality manufactured character artifacts: PIXI’s die cast metal, Leblond et Delienne’s plaster casts, Michel Aroutcheff’s resin or wood renditions of popular European and American characters were soon seen displayed in comic book store windows.

Make no mistake - character toy not quite, these objects nevertheless exert the same aura on their owners, pulling them back into past narratives and providing them with the feeling that the fetishised hero obtained at high cost has transposed its magical powers to its owner.

“Toy as art is now a culture sandwiched between the dollar and the heart... trouble is, a toy treated exclusively as a commodity loses its artistic dimension. Worse still, it loses any meaning when its market value shoots to sky-rocketing heights.” (Marwick)

Or does it? The sharks Marwick feared the rise of have settled around us, off and online, exploiting our need for a sense of meaningful identity in an alienating consumer society. Character toy design entrepreneurs such as Jeremy (Jeremyville) and Paul Budnitz (KidRobot), brushing aside accusations of dusty Peter Pan syndrome nostalgia, live off quite well from a phenomenon that mixes youth culture, product innovation and technology, reveling in the cultural catch 22 conundrum Matt Mason describes in “The Pirate’s Dilemma”. Subverting advanced capitalism’s marketing and branding strategies while highjacking street fashion and counter-culture references, these entrepreneurs redefine capitalism, laughing on their way to the bank as they apply on their own pop terms Andy Warhol’s creed that “Business is the highest form of art”.

Toys bear with them their society’s stigma – only ten years after WWII at a time when the toy and mass media industries were shifting into full distribution gear in the West and in Japan, Barthes was deploring toys’ bourgeois, normalizing streak.

Yet toys can – as has been the case over the past few decades with the blending of pop culture into many character toys – channel the fantastical, whimsical, poetic, humorous, or even critical take expressed by artists, humourists or philosophers – all those who question the world as it is. Character toys, strong bearers of connotations as they are, bridge icon and object. As toy historian Léo Clarétie explained in 1901: “The toy industry embraces, in fantasy and whimsicality, the most exquisite of all crafts combined”: more so than with any other object History can be read through the symbolic imagery conveyed by (character) toys. It is no mere coincidence that Paris’ Musée des Arts Décoratifs’ Toy Gallery’s inaugural exhibition was dedicated to character toys.

Eternity is art’s domain. To borrow from Malraux, “Beyond its birth ties, art often spills over – sometimes transcends – its civilization.”

Yet character toys have a very short commercial lifespan and are subject to the businesses’ seasonal imperatives: annual festivals (i.e. Christmas) during which the consumer market focuses on gifts for children.

Time's ongoing acceleration and compression puts tremendous pressure on design and artistic creativity. In this context, just as they surprise their parents in their ease at connecting to wired systems, children are happy to indulge in the seemingly headless variety of cultural references on offer in this multicultural soup. Reversely, adults in need of cultural anchorage may find it difficult to decode the many cultural references behind products marketed for global consumption.

Children are happy to pocket absurdity (the basis for humour) – think Pokemon – and gather around them a bestiary populated by the silly *and* the smart, the cute *and* the monstrous, the gooey *and* the neat, the menacing *and* the heroic, or the beastly *with* the beautiful.

Character Toy NEXT: an On and Offline affair

Much has changed over the past decade, with the explosion of designer and artist character toys, the absorption of popular child mythology by young adults in Cosplay practices, the incessant creation of characters for video games, or games that incessantly allow you to create characters such as The SIMS creator Will Wright's SPORE; or merchandisers' development of character-based branding strategies.

How will design articulate character toys' future relevance to emotional identity? How safe can I feel developing and sharing happy playful narratives if my fun; worse still, if my dreams are branded? How will I know if my dreams are mine? Youth culture seems to be comfortable linking self-actualisation – an achievement Abraham Maslov says is attainable to only 2% of us – to branding strategies.

Does anything generated through play need to resemble something? Children, especially younger ones, will tinker with whatever comes in their grasp – including parts of their own broken toys – and make sense of their assemblages on their own terms.

“What a child wants is not the toy but the play. The more necessary play is, the more tolerant the child towards its formal canon of representation, the arbitrary nature of the toy. Children of all times would recognize a car in a matchbox.” (Borras)

So how relevant are (physical) character toys to today's children? The toy manufacturing industry is in disarray as it observes children losing interest in tangible playthings.

Contemporary youth is moving away from toy-centred play which until recently *necessarily* included an object (Sutton-Smith), to electronic or online game play, relegating toy-play to children too young to pick up a controller or click a mouse. The scope of toys has expanded to include “wired” play, featuring multimedia platforms connecting virtual communities who share

experiences, accrue knowledge (learn), and disseminate information - online. One shapes new narratives as it follows the ever-changing transformations of characters alive in cyber worlds such as Nickelodeon's virtual-pet website Neopets, a 100-million-plus online community of game players following the lives of dozens of virtual characters; or Second Life, where older youth and adults can create and exist as their better-ego.

What of robotics, then? Technology sophisticated enough for machines to emotionally relate to humans and share our need for symbolic access to the imaginary through characters is also embedded in robotic solutions, especially in Japan, where one does not see the electro-mechanical "other" as a threat as is often the case in American science-fiction literature. On the contrary, companies like Honda and Sony are refining solutions for mechanical soulmates that sooner more than later could express emotions similar to humans' – to the extent that robots could be programmed to desire or reject a partner – dynamics crucial to the sentiment of love, as they indicate that love is neither unconditional nor eternal (Evans). Ironically, as toys currently disappear online, their lives could eventually come to tangible realities in the form of character-bots ready for play and adventure...

To interpret the world on one's own terms, to reinvent it, is an act of freedom. To refuse to look like anybody else is a sign of intellectual freedom. What kind of toy, or if we consider the disappearance of the "physical" toy, what kind of multiple toy & media platform will help fulfill such ambitions? "The simplest construction toy implies a very unique apprenticeship of the world: the child in no way creates significant objects, and is not concerned with giving them adult names: what he executes is not function, but a demiurgy: he creates life, not a property; where objects behave on their own accord." (Barthes)

The design of future character toys may require an understanding of children's unspoiled perspective on a world that is necessarily a universe of endless wonderment and discovery. The following suggestions may provide possible leads:

The odder the merrier: Children are very comfortable playing with zany characters, quirky playpals and wacky games from another dimension. Meet my friend the Monster under the bed. or the Giant Microbes.

Living with the "inhuman": Will entertainment robotics bridge the "uncanny valley"? What form will 3D interactive artificial companions take in a world of omnipresent screens? Technology-embedded artificial critters will oscillate between two emotional poles: an E-

volution of techno engineering wonder gadgets and an E-den of sensor-stuffed interactive pets and companions.

Constructing worlds, manipulating life: As we see with Sandra Higashi and Byron Glaser's construction set Zolo, shapes are now a given in construction toys. Interactive parts, as seen in Logiblocks, combined with materials used in sex toys or novelty products could also widen the scope of synesthetic possibilities when manipulating the emotions of characters to come.

Wacky senses: Future character toys will have to offer rich sensory experiences: children are happy to experiment with sight, touch, sound, smell, and taste, on their own terms, with silly tricks and gooey treats, away from their parents' clinical dictate, as seen with such playsets as Goey Louie.

"Kawaii or Kakoi Karakta"?: Cute or macho? Sassy or cool? The blurring of the lines between genders will further reshape Toyland's established gender-specific landscape: young males and females explore aspects of identity traditionally the domain of the opposite sex: while boys seem more and more concerned with their looks, girls are happy to assert a sassier sense of self.

Body fantastic: Just as X-treme sports and Paralympics are gaining in popularity, the fashion industry has absorbed sportswear's ready-for-action aesthetics: a generation more than ever aware of - or obsessed with - its body wants TOTAL control over our physical and emotional limits.

Toy Content + Good Branding = the Branded ME™: Are Bratz™ My Scene™? Is Cosplay Brand-play? While toy company managers are busy discussing "content" – play value based on narrative structures, game theory, linguistics, interaction, and fashion trends, content providers and programmers define emotionally appropriate responses to the interactive processes players are engaged in when dealing with smart toys – a means to substantiate their brand's cultural relevance and credibility with appropriate toy marketing DNA: Brand = Character = Content.

Wired personalities: The ubiquitous nature of cyberspace allows players to be anything. With the increasing connectivity of new toys and their extension onto multisensory virtual platforms, make-believe is cast with changeable characters: a nobody becomes somebody, everybody, anytime, anywhere, playing an ever malleable game of identity.

Conclusion: From Character Toys to Character Boys – and Girls

Paradoxically, the progressive sophistication of manufacturing techniques could lead to a semantic void, to the disappearance of signs too connoted, too “present”, and a design of truly virtual play, where toys would be kept unfinished, delivered as potential for emotionally rich experiences.

“If the adult could avoid resorting to the toy to adapt the child to a society he wishes to perpetuate in its image, and renounce to an international industry, who knows whether the child could therefore create its own toys, which we could not say whether they are educational, which we would not say tomorrow that they are poetic, but which he will consider a very personal thing, emotionally rich from its creative endeavour, imperfect yet gratifying.

If such a utopia were to come true, toys would pave children the way for the most enviable and wonderful adventure. The child who will create its own toys will be able to create tomorrow the world we dream of.” (Borras)

Following the elimination of the character, a character toy designer’s ambition would turn away from the toy – only to focus on the *character boy*, or *girl*. While youth culture happily manipulates signs the consumer industry relentlessly injects in its mental environment, it is now redefining how capitalism’s cycle of production and consumption identifies itself. Players whom today are given the means to create their own imaginary world will create tomorrow’s characters – for all players to brand as their own.

May 2008

References

Barthes, Roland, *Mythologies*, Seuil, 1957 (original ed.), Hill and Wang (translation), 1972

Baudrillard, Jean, *The System of Objects*, Gallimard, 1968 (original ed.), Verso (translation), 2006

Bigle, Gérard, *Droits Derivés, Licences et Character Merchandising*, Paris: Masson/Delmas, 1987

Bloemink, Barbara J., Merino, Ana, Gribenas, Rick, Clark, Vicky A., *Comic Release: Negotiating Identity for a New Generation*, (Paperback), D.A.P./Distributed Art Publishers, Inc., 2003

Borras, Maria Lluisa, *Le Monde des Jouets*, Poligrafa. S.A., Barcelone 1969

Calcutt, Andrew, *Arrested Development: Pop Culture and the Erosion of Adulthood*, Cassell, UK, 1998

Evans, Dylan, *Emotion: The Science of Sentiment*, Oxford University Press, 2001

Jeremy, *Vinyl Will Kill: An Inside Look at the Designer Toy Phenomenon*, Gingko Press, 2007

Lacayo, Richard, *If Everybody Is Hip... Is Anybody Hip?* Time Magazine, August 8th, 1994

Lubow, Arthur, *The Murakami Method*, The New York Times, April 3rd, 2005

Mason, Matt, *The Pirate's Dilemma: How Youth Culture Is Reinventing Capitalism*, Free Press, 2007

Mirpuri, Dipika, *Top 10 Licensed Characters For Toys For The Coming Year*, Toy Blog, March 2, 2005 <http://toys.about.com/od/toyfair2005/tp/toptoylicenses.htm>

Perry, George, and Aldridge, Alan, *The Penguin Book of Comics*, Penguin Graphic Fiction, (Paperback), 1967

Poirier, Jean, *Histoire des Moeurs*, Gallimard, Paris 2002

O'Neill, Brendan, *Why Nostalgia's Not What it Used to Be*, BBC News, February 6 2004 http://news.bbc.co.uk/go/pr/fr/-/2/hi/uk_news/magazine/3465231.stm

Spodek, Bernard, and Saracho, Olivia N. Ed., *Handbook of Research on the Education of Young Children*, Routledge 2006

Sutton-Smith, Brian, *Toys as Culture*, Gardner Press, 1986

TDC - Toy Trends Review December 4th 2007 – Hong Kong Industry Profiles

http://toys.tdctrade.com/content.aspx?data=toys_content_en&contentid=174001&w_sid=194&w_pid=713&w_nid=11808&w_cid=2&w_idt=1900-01-01

Twitchell, James B., *Adcult USA: The Triumph of Advertising in American Culture*, Columbia University Press, 1996

Wilensky, Dawn, Toys Have 'License' to Thrill - Licensed Toy Properties Are Turning Into Brands, *Discount Store News*, Feb 5 1996